

Title: **Project website**
Deliverable number: **D6.1**
Revision 1 - Status: **Final**
Date of issue: **22/03/2019**

Project website

Deliverable title	Project website
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1) Location and purpose of the website

The website of PAPILA was established in May 2018 (month 5 of PAPILA) and is accessible at www.papila-h2020.eu, physically located at a server of MPI-M. It ensures the representation and communication of PAPILA during the lifetime of the project and beyond.

Currently the website is divided into a *publicly accessible part*, containing basic information about the project (list of partners, scientific objectives, potential users of PAPILA products, etc.), and a password-protected *Intranet*, which is accessible for PAPILA partners only.

The website will serve as one of the main dissemination channels of PAPILA results, including links to PAPILA product pages and other relevant information.

Figure 1: Screenshot of the PAPILA home page (taken on 21 March 2019)

2) Content management system

The contents of the website are edited by means of the TYPO3 Content Management System, which is an open source free tool used at MPI-M. It is relatively easy to handle, and several PAPILA partners have already a password with writing access to the website.

3) List of users of PAPILA products

Deliverable D6.1 is a combination of ‘Prototype website’ and ‘List of potential users’ which were two separate deliverables in the PAPILA proposal. The combined deliverable D6.1 was due at month 12 of PAPILA (December 2018), coinciding with the planned secondment of researchers from the University of Chile to MET Norway, during which the list of users should be created. That secondments was postponed to February 2019, which is the reason for the slight delay of D6.1 to March 2019. However, the first part of the deliverable (i.e. the website) was accomplished well in time (first half of 2018).

The list of users of PAPILA products was created, as planned, during the secondment of Prof. Laura Gallardo-Klenner to MET Norway in February 2019 and was put on the publicly accessible PAPILA web page <http://papila-h2020.eu/index.php?id=5075> (there it is given without contact details).

The full list, including contact details will be accessible through the intranet and is also reprinted here below in its current version. It will be subject to change and additions during the lifetime of PAPILA, based on input from all PAPILA partners and their contact networks.

Table 1: List of potential users of PAPILA products (version 3.1, 4th March 2019), including contact details where available.

Countries represented in PAPILA	Institution	Contact Person
Argentina	Servicio Meteorológico Nacional (Argentinean Weather Service) https://www.smn.gov.ar/	Celeste Saulo Director of the Argentinean National Meteorological Service (SMN) (Second Vice-President of the World Meteorological Organization) csaulo@smn.gov.ar
	Centro de Investigaciones del Mar y la Atmósfera (CIMA), Universidad de Buenos Aires (UBA)(Center for Ocean and Atmosphere Research, University of Buenos Aires) http://www.cima.fcen.uba.ar/	Claudia Simionato Director of Centro de Investigaciones del Mar y la Atmósfera (CIMA), Universidad de Buenos Aires simionato@cima.fcen.uba.ar
	Comisión Nacional de Energía Atómica (National Atomic Energy Commission of Argentina) https://www.argentina.gob.ar/comision-nacional-de-energia-atmica	Laura Dawidowski dawidows@cnea.gov.ar
	Agencia de Protección Ambiental, Gobierno de la Ciudad de Buenos Aires. https://www.buenosaires.gob.ar/ambienteypaciopublico/agencia-de-proteccion-ambiental	Juan Bautista Filgueira jbfilgueira@buenosaires.gob.ar
	Organismo Provincial para el Desarrollo Sostenible. Gobierno de la Provincia de Buenos Aires http://wwwa.opds.gba.gov.ar/	Ricargo Pabla. Executive Director TBD

Countries represented in PAPILA	Institution	Contact Person
Bolivia	Servicio Nacional de Meteorología e Hidrología (SENAMHI) de Bolivia (Bolivian Weather Service) http://senamhi.gob.bo/index.php/inicio	Gualberto Carrasco Director General SENAMHI carrasco@senamhi.gob.bo
	Secretaría Municipal de Gestión Ambiental Gobierno Municipal Autónomo de La Paz (Municipality of La Paz, Environmental Management Secretariat) https://www.lapaz.bo/gobierno/smga/	Mariana Daza von Boeck Directora de Gestión ambiental de La Paz mariana.daza@lapaz.bo
	Dirección de Gestión y Control Ambiental del Gobierno Municipal de El Alto (Municipality of El Alto, Direction of Management and Environmental Control)	TBD
Brazil	Companhia Ambiental do Estado de São Paulo (CETESB) (Environmental Agency of Sao Paulo) https://cetesb.sp.gov.br/	Patrícia Faga Iglecias Lemos Director CETESB e-mail pending
	Universidade Federal das Pelotas, Faculdade de Meteorologia https://wp.ufpel.edu.br/meteorologia/	Marcelo F. Alonso Faculdade de Meteorologia marcelo.alonso@ufpel.edu.br
	Pontificia Universidade Católica do Rio de Janeiro http://www.qui.puc-rio.br/	Adriana Gioda Faculdade de Química agioda@puc-rio.br
	Departamento de Ciências Atmosféricas e Climáticas, Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Norte (UFRGN) https://www1.ccet.ufrn.br/ciencias-atmosfericas-e-climaticas/	Judith Hoelzemann Deputy Director Department of Atmosphere and Climate Science judith.hoelzemann@ccet.ufrn.br
	Poluição do Ar e Processos Atmosféricos Universidade Tecnológica Federal do Paraná http://www.utfpr.edu.br/londrina	Leila Doprichinski Martins leilamartins@utfpr.edu.br
	Departamento de Engenharia Sanitária e Ambiental (DESA) Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais (UFMG)	Taciana Albuquerque tacianatoledo26@gmail.com
	Universidade Federal de Alagoas, Instituto de Ciências Atmosféricas (UFAL/ICAT), Maceió, Alagoas,	Rosiberto Salustiano rosibertojr@gmail.com
	Instituto Tecnológico de Aeronáutica, Departamento de Ciência e Tecnologia Aeroespacial, São José dos Campos, SP, Brasil.	Gilberto Fisch Fisch.gilberto@gmail.com
	CPTEC – Centro de Previsão de tempo e estudos climáticos	Dirceu Herdies Dirceu.herdies@inpe.br
CEMADEN Centro Nacional de Monitoramento e Alertas de Desastres Naturais, Estrada Doutor Altino Bondensan, 500 – Distrito Eugênio de Melo, São José dos Campos	Oswaldo Moraes osvaldo.moraes@cemaden.gov.br	

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Chile	División Calidad del Aire Ministerio de Medio Ambiente (MMA) http://portal.mma.gob.cl/tag/division-de-calidad-del-aire/	Marcelo Fernández Gómez Head of Division mfernandez@mma.gob.cl
	Dirección Meteorológica de Chile (DMC) (Chilean Weather Service) http://www.meteochile.gob.cl/PortalDMC-web/index.xhtml	Ricardo Alcaful Quezada Head for Research and Technological Support ricardo@meteochile.cl
	Intendencia Región Metropolitana de Santiago (Regional Government for Santiago) http://www.intendenciametropolitana.gov.cl/	Karla Rubilar Barahona Intendenta de Santiago +56 (2) 26765812, +56 226765813
	Red Chilena de Municipios contra el Cambio Climático (Network of Chilean municipalities against climate change) http://www.redmunicc.cl/esp/	TBD
Colombia	Contaminación Ambiental Instituto de Meteorología y Estudios Ambientales (IDEAM) http://www.ideam.gov.co/web/contaminacion-y-calidad-ambiental/	Gabriel Saldarriaga Coordinador Grupo Operación de Redes Ambientales gsaldarriaga@ideam.gov.co
	Secretaría Distrital del Ambiente Bogotá http://www.ambientebogota.gov.co/calidad-del-aire	Oscar Alexander Ducuara Subdirector de Calidad del Aire, Visual y Auditiva oscar.ducuara@ambientebogota.gov.co
	Área Metropolitana de Bucaramanga	Oscar Rojas +57 300 8820382
	Departamento Administrativo de Gestión del Medio Ambiente – Alcaldía de Santiago de Cali	Gisella Arizabaleta garizabaleta@hotmail.com
	Corporación Autónoma Regional del Valle del Cauca	Germán Restrepo german.restrepo@cvc.gov.co
	Barranquilla Verde – Alcaldía de Barranquilla	Margarita Castillo Ramírez Coordinadora SVCA Margarita.castillo@barranquillaverde.gov.co
	Corporación Autónoma Regional de Boyacá – Corpoboyacá	Mauricio Rojas mrojast60@hotmail.com
	Corporación Autónoma Regional del Cesar	Álvaro Zuleta +57 311 4136841
	Universidad Nacional de Colombia	Néstor Rojas Profesor Asociado nyrojas@unal.edu.co
	Sistema de Alertas Tempranas de Medellín System from Medellín (SIATA) https://siata.gov.co/siata_nuevo/	Laura Herrera laura.herrera@siata.gov.co
Universidad de Antioquia, Medellín Environmental School	Ángela María Rendón Profesora Asistente angela.rendon@udea.edu.co	

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Venezuela	Centro de Ciencias Atmosféricas y Biogeoquímica, Instituto Venezolano de Investigaciones Científicas (IVIC) http://www.ivic.gob.ve/es/investigacion-3/centros-31/centro-de-ciencias-atmosfericas-y-biogeoquimica-ccab	Loreto Donoso Email: loretoeliana@gmail.com Tibisay Perez Email: tibisay.j.perez@gmail.com Aptdo. 20632. Caracas 1020-A, Venezuela Phone: +58-212-504-1210 / -1417
	Instituto Nacional de Meteorología e Hidrología (INAMEH) http://www.inameh.gob.ve/web/index.php	TBD
Mexico	Pronóstico de Calidad de Aire Gobierno de la Ciudad de México http://www.aire.cdmx.gob.mx/pronostico-aire/	TBD
	Servicio Meteorológico Nacional https://smn.cna.gob.mx	TBD
Puerto Rico	Department of Environmental Science University of Puerto Rico, Puerto Rico http://envsci.uprrp.edu/	Olga L. Mayol-Bracero, Atmospheric Chemistry and Aerosols Research (ACAR) Department of Environmental Science University of Puerto Rico - Rio Piedras San Juan, PR 00925-2537 USA Office phone: +1 787 764-0000 Ext. 88191 or 88220 (secretary) Lab phone: +1 787 764-0000 Ext. 88191, 88192 E-mail: omayol@ites.upr.edu
	Área de Calidad del Aire Junta de Calidad Ambiental de Puerto Rico http://www.agencias.pr.gov/agencias/jca/areas_programaticas/Pages/%c3%81rea-Calidad-de-Aire.aspx	TBD
Other countries		
Costa Rica	<u>Dirección de Gestión de Calidad Ambiental</u> <u>Ministerio de Ambiente y Energía (MINAE)</u> http://www.digeca.go.cr/areas/gestion-de-la-calidad-del-aire	TBD digeca@minae.go.cr
Ecuador	Secretaría de Ambiente Alcaldía de Quito http://www.quitoambiente.gob.ec/ambiente/index.php/calidad-del-aire	TBD
Paraguay	Dirección de Meteorología e Hidrología http://www.meteorologia.gov.py/	TBD
	Dirección General del Aire Secretaría del Ambiente	TBD
Uruguay	Universidad de la República	
	Calidad del Aire Intendencia de la Ciudad de Montevideo http://www.montevideo.gub.uy/calidad-del-aire	TBD